

**APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF THE UNIVERSITY: TECHNOLOGIES,
POTENTIAL AND PROBLEMS**

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***Abstract:** The article shows that the potential of artificial intelligence is associated with the successful solution of routine tasks of the educational process, however, the conceptual connections of the subject being studied, value-semantic assessments, and the educational component are inaccessible to the machine. Artificial intelligence opens up many new opportunities and should be implemented as an auxiliary tool for teachers. The introduction of self-learning digital programs into the educational process creates a number of serious social problems. Therefore, it is proposed to develop tools for public control over the development of artificial intelligence technologies, which involve limiting the freedom of creativity in this area.*

***Key words:** artificial intelligence, educational process, artificial intelligence technologies, artificial intelligence potential, problems of robotization of the educational process.*

ntroduction. A distinctive feature of modern society is the desire for informatization in all spheres of human life. One of the most progressive and relevant forms of informatization is the process of introducing artificial intelligence into the daily life of society, including education. In the scientific literature, intelligent learning systems (ILS) [1, etc.], based on the use of artificial intelligence technologies, are considered as an effective means of improving the quality of education. Of considerable interest to researchers is the problem of the

potential of artificial intelligence technologies in the educational process. It is discussed in two aspects: the first is related to the assessment of the possibilities of personalized learning [2], the second concerns the assessment of the ability of artificial intelligence technologies to displace a living teacher from the educational process [3]. Purpose of the study. Based on the consideration of artificial intelligence technologies and the potential of its use in the educational process of the university, identify application problems and propose an idea about how to solve these problems.

Research methodology. To understand the processes in modern education, which are significantly influenced by the fourth industrial revolution taking place in the world, it is necessary to use a sociocultural method that allows taking into account the most important feature of this revolution - the digitalization of all spheres of public life, an integral element of which is robotization.

Results and discussion. At the beginning of the study, we will clarify what is meant by the term "artificial intelligence". It should be borne in mind that it is used in different senses.

In reference publications, the concept of "artificial intelligence" is defined as the ability of computer intelligent systems to perform traditional human creative functions. [2 and others]. In the scientific literature, artificial intelligence refers to technological systems that rely on a Big Data repository for decision making and operate on the principle of an algorithm. Often the concept of "artificial intelligence" means a digital program capable of self-learning and development, objectified in some kind of machine shell. The literature describes the main artificial intelligence programs used in the educational process. We consider it inappropriate to reproduce known material. Let's focus on the main thing. In our opinion, the main achievement in the application of artificial intelligence is the possibility of personalized learning. Artificial intelligence technologies using software platforms based on neural networks and big data (Big Data) create an

opportunity to raise the idea of personalization of education to a qualitatively new level, since neural networks often offer unique solutions that ordinary human thinking is not capable of. To implement the orientation towards personalization of learning, specialized digital programs have been created that allow taking into account the individual characteristics of students, providing sufficient results for some and accelerated and in-depth education for others. The implementation of personalized learning programs significantly transforms the traditional system of higher education, stimulating the refusal of universities from a single curriculum, the transition from standards and unification of the educational process to its individualization. This transformation raises a number of questions. First: is it possible to create and implement methods of the educational process that meet the needs of society without control by specialized regulatory and supervisory bodies? Second: is it permissible to entrust the process of creating methods of the educational process to digital programs? Third: how safe is it for the individual and society to introduce such innovations into the educational process? Representatives of the scientific community are well aware that any self-learning digital program is a constantly changing and improving set of logical standards, and people are not always able to understand the logic of self-developing artificial intelligence [2].

The scientific community also notes the ongoing significant changes in the nature of the work of artificial intelligence programs. In particular, if in the original programs the result of their work was big data, but these programs themselves were passive, then at the level of self-learning digital systems, big data began to control options. And this means an increase in the unpredictability of their work, since it is no longer programmers, but the data itself that determines what to do next. In addition to the unpredictability of the results of the work of self-learning digital systems, there also arises such an important problem of individualized learning as the criteria for the final assessment of learning

outcomes, because if uniform requirements are excluded from the educational process and replaced by individual programs, then the final knowledge of the student should become individual and unique. Thus, instead of a set of competencies that are determined by regulatory documents (FSES), each student, on the basis of an individual plan formed by artificial intelligence programs, also develops a unique set of competencies. As noted above, on the basis of artificial intelligence, programs for assessing students' achievements in the educational process have been developed and are being applied. However, it is not known to what extent an artificial intelligence program is able to give an adequate, from the point of view of human values, assessment of the results of mastering educational programs in the sense that pedagogical assessment is not only an assessment of the level of knowledge of the subject, but also has an educational, often stimulating value for the student. As you know, in the practice of using artificial intelligence programs, there were cases when the work of the program got out of control of people due to a peculiar arrangement of priorities [3]. It follows that it is impossible to guarantee the adequate operation of such programs. In addition to methodological problems, the use of artificial intelligence programs in the educational process has created a serious social problem: the possibility of reducing the staff of teachers and university staff. The comprehension of these problems raised the question for the educational community: is it necessary and possible to fight against the introduction of artificial intelligence programs in the educational process? In response to this question, various opinions have formed in the educational community. In particular, there is a trend of negative attitude towards the introduction of artificial intelligence in education. Supporters of this trend believe that the introduction of machine learning technologies dehumanizes the educational process, which requires such human qualities as empathy and compassion. At the same time, the opposite opinion has also formed in the scientific and pedagogical community, which is based on two ideas. First, the

development of technology is an objective process and cannot be stopped. Secondly, artificial intelligence programs do not replace teachers, but perform auxiliary functions, significantly improving the learning process. According to University College London (UCL) professor Rose Lakin, “The potential for using AI to make the learning process manageable and visual is enormous. The task of such implementations should not be to replace a person and not to force him out, but on the contrary: the use of AI as an additional tool” [3]. Recognizing the important role of informatization in improving the education system, we must not forget that education is the unity of training and education. Obviously, the educational component cannot be transferred to artificial intelligence programs, it remains with a living teacher. In the educational process, he acts not just as a carrier and translator of information. First of all, he is a Teacher: the bearer of value-semantic constructs, for students - an example to follow. The emotional component plays an important role in the educational process, and it is realized only in the interaction of the teacher and the student, as well as students with each other, whose contacts are organized by the teacher. Conclusions and conclusion. Our goal was to explore the potential and problems of existing artificial intelligence technologies in the educational process of the university and develop a position on the acceptable limits of its application. The study found that the use of artificial intelligence is multilateral. The most important resource of artificial intelligence technologies in higher education is related to the possibilities of personalization.

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